

The Mediating Role of Place Attachment, Attitudes, and Satisfaction in Loyalty to Film Tourism Destinations

El papel mediador del apego al lugar, las actitudes y la satisfacción en la lealtad hacia destinos turísticos cinematográficos

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Abstract

In recent decades, the surge in new content platforms and formats has led to an 85% increase in mobile TV and video consumption since 2010. Concurrently, audiovisual content such as films and series has become pivotal in boosting the popularity of destinations and influencing tourists' travel decisions. Consumers increasingly seek products and services that offer added value, including symbolic elements and distinctive experiences. Film tourism has experienced significant growth, driven by enhanced travel accessibility and the democratisation of tourism globally. This study employs a literature review and empirical analysis to examine how place attachment, attitudes, and satisfaction mediate the relationship between perceived value and loyalty towards cinematic tourism destinations. By integrating cognitive and emotional constructs, the study proposes a comprehensive model that advances the understanding of tourist behaviour in the context of film-induced tourism. The results confirm that both emotional connection and satisfaction significantly affect destination loyalty. The findings provide valuable insights for destination managers to effectively leverage film tourism trends and foster sustainable tourism development through more emotionally engaging and memorable experiences.

Keywords: Film tourism, Travel destination, Loyalty, Satisfaction, Film-induced tourism, Place Attachment.

Resumen

En las últimas décadas, el auge de nuevas plataformas y formatos de contenido ha provocado un aumento del 85 % en el consumo de televisión y video móvil desde 2010. Paralelamente, los contenidos audiovisuales, como películas y series, se han convertido en factores clave para impulsar la popularidad de los destinos e influir en las decisiones de viaje de los turistas. Los consumidores buscan cada vez más productos y servicios que ofrezcan un valor añadido, incluyendo elementos simbólicos y experiencias distintivas. El turismo cinematográfico ha experimentado un notable crecimiento, impulsado por una mayor accesibilidad a los viajes y la democratización del turismo a nivel global. Este estudio emplea una revisión de la literatura y un análisis empírico para examinar cómo el apego al lugar, las actitudes y la satisfacción median la relación entre el valor percibido y la lealtad hacia destinos turísticos cinematográficos. Al integrar dimensiones cognitivas y emocionales, se propone un modelo integral que permite comprender mejor el comportamiento del turista. Los resultados ofrecen información relevante para gestores turísticos interesados en fomentar un desarrollo turístico sostenible mediante experiencias más memorables y emocionalmente significativas.

Palabras-chave/Palabras clave: Turismo cinematográfico, Destino Turístico, Lealtad, Satisfacción, Turismo Inducido por el Cine, Apego al Lugar.

1. Introduction

In the contemporary era, there is a discernible transition from conventional consumption patterns towards pursuing products and services that offer enhanced value and distinctive experiences (Brandão et al., 2023; Roy & Gretzel, 2020; Zhang et al., 2021). This transformation is discernible in the tourism industry, where postmodernist perspectives are supplanting the mass-consumption paradigm. This shift reflects a predilection for travel experiences that are distinctive and culturally rooted (Tiwari et al., 2023; Uslu et al., 2024).

One of the most dynamic manifestations of this shift is film-induced tourism, a phenomenon driven by the global expansion of the entertainment industry and increased accessibility to international travel (Hudson & Ritchie, 2006). The tourism sector has undergone a significant transformation, moving away from the traditional sun-and-beach model towards a more diverse and

technology-driven experience (Sharma et al., 2024). This shift has been driven by advances in digital platforms and audiovisual content, as evidenced by the findings of Zielinski and Botero (2019), Picazo and Moreno-Gil (2019), Arefieva et al. (2021), Cao et al. (2021), and Nguyen and Tong (2023). Notwithstanding the disruptions occasioned by the pandemic, the tourism sector continues to represent a pivotal economic sector, with social media and video content assuming a pivotal role for travellers (Cox et al., 2009). Film tourism, in particular, leverages the power of audiovisual media to create symbolic and emotional connections between tourists and destinations, offering an innovative and sustainable approach to destination branding (Masset et al., 2024). In this context, film-induced tourism has emerged as a particularly innovative and forward-thinking form of tourism, reflecting the dynamic evolution of the industry (Aguilar-Rivero et al., 2023).

Despite the increasing academic interest in film tourism, a crucial research gap remains: the limited understanding of how place attachment and attitudes jointly mediate the relationship between perceived value (PV) and destination loyalty. While prior studies acknowledge the impact of PV on place attachment and loyalty, they often overlook the combined mediating role of attitudes, such as service quality perceptions, alongside emotional attachment. This study addresses this conceptual shortcoming by integrating both emotional and cognitive dimensions into a unified theoretical framework.

Additionally, while the influence of perceived value on loyalty and the mediating role of satisfaction have been separately examined, a comprehensive model incorporating satisfaction as a key mediator has not been fully established. This research contributes to the literature by demonstrating how satisfaction, attitudes, and place attachment collectively shape tourist loyalty in the context of film tourism. By bridging these gaps, the study provides a novel and holistic perspective on the interplay between emotional connections, cognitive evaluations, and behavioural intentions in cinematic tourism experiences.

2. Literature review

2.1 Film-induced tourism

The tourism industry plays a crucial role on the global stage, with a significant economic impact. The United Nations World Tourism Organisation (UNWTO, 2024) reports that the industry's contribution to global GDP rebounded to pre-pandemic levels in 2023, reaching approximately \$3.3 trillion, representing 3% of the world's GDP. Over time, tourism has undergone various paradigm shifts. Harrill et al. (2022) highlight a move from traditional business-centric approaches to a more nuanced, postmodern research focus.

Academic literature offers various definitions to address film tourism conceptually. Croy and Heitmann (2011) suggest that film tourism encompasses several elements, including its role as a tourism motivator, the integration of cinema into holiday experiences, celebrity tourism, cinematic nostalgia, film-related attractions, movie tours, cinematic theme parks, film festivals, and the notion of cinema as a form of vicarious travel. Other studies, such as those by Kim and Kim (2017), Roesch (2009), and Wray and Croy (2015), indicate that film tourism emerges from the transformation of filming locations into spaces that evoke nostalgia in audiences, driven by the stories and events associated with these sites. Similarly, Araújo et al. (2021) emphasise that film tourism arises from the intersection of tourism and the audiovisual sector, specifically through film-induced tourism, characterised by tourist visits to destinations depicted or portrayed in films.

As Croy (2011) described, film tourism involves the attraction and influence that films exert on tourists, establishing a connection between cinematic experiences and travel behaviours. Croy and Heitmann (2011) expand on this by identifying various forms of film tourism, including celebrity tourism, cinematic nostalgia, and film-related attractions. Cardoso et al. (2017) further broaden the concept to include the entire spectrum of audiovisual media and related tourist activities. According to Araújo et al. (2021), film tourism specifically involves visiting locations depicted in movies.

The impact of film tourism is evident from the surge in tourist numbers, which rose from 40 million in 2012 to 80 million in 2018 (TCI Research, 2018). Furthermore, the increased utilisation of mobile devices has resulted in an 85% surge in television and video consumption since 2010 (Ericsson ConsumerLab, 2017). This expansion, though not novel, serves to illustrate the growing interest in the audiovisual sector and has resulted in the identification of distinctive filming locations that have attracted leading industry professionals (Araújo et al., 2021; Araújo-Vila et al., 2024).

Film tourism offers several advantages, particularly its non-seasonal nature, which contrasts with the traditional focus on sun-and-beach tourism that has dominated coastal regions since the mid-20th century (Zielinski et al., 2019). This distinctive dynamic makes film tourism a compelling alternative, offering a fresh approach to managing and redefining crowded destinations (Depken et al., 2020; Domínguez-Azcue et al., 2021). As tourism destinations evolve, there is a need for innovation in tourism models, moving away from outdated approaches to meet the changing preferences of travellers who seek more authentic experiences (Zhang et al., 2021; Aguilar-Rivero et al., 2024). Film tourism, in particular, enhances a destination's appeal and shapes tourist behaviour (Hao et al., 2024).

2.2 Perceived value

Chiu et al. (2014) propose that perceived value stems from evaluating the benefits and costs of services and products, considering factors like service, price, and quality. These benefits and costs shape tourists' attitudes and behaviours (Rasoolimanesh et al., 2016), with the overall evaluation reflecting the perceived utility of what is received in exchange for what is given (Zeithaml, 1988).

Perceived value may be shaped by various emotions and attitudes a tourist experiences when acquiring a specific product or service (Jamal et al., 2011). This encompasses not only the cost but also the psychological factors and perceived quality of the product and the overall experience (Chen & Hu, 2010).

The analysis of destination image is particularly compelling, as it offers insights into how tourists perceive a destination and whether this perception influences their behaviour, which is crucial for effectively managing and promoting these locations (Wu & Liang, 2020). The value tourists assign to a destination can be highly subjective, rooted in their personal impressions of the place and their thoughts and emotions at the time (Huete-Alcocer & Hernández-Rojas, 2022). In this context, and linking this concept to film tourism, destination image encompasses cognitive and affective images, including those influenced by films and cultural heritage (Zhang & Lo, 2023).

Perceived value pertains to the consumer's assessment of a product or service's utility, considering its benefits and drawbacks (Zhang et al., 2022). It is recognised as a critical determinant influencing tourists' behaviour and their future intentions (Yi et al., 2014). Within the tourism sector, perceived value has been demonstrated to positively influence the likelihood of tourists returning to a destination (Rasoolimanesh et al., 2023). Mechinda et al. (2009) argue that both perceived value and tourist satisfaction at a destination positively impact the development of loyalty. Nonetheless, these relationships have not been explored in the field of film tourism, even though they have been empirically supported in various other tourism domains. We suggest that these effects might also apply to film tourism.

Accordingly, we put forward the following research hypothesis: Perceived value positively and directly affects loyalty towards a film destination (**H1**).

2.3 Place attachment

Attachment theory offers a comprehensive framework for understanding the development of emotional bonds (Krolikowska et al., 2020). It describes attachment as the human tendency to seek and form emotional connections with specific objects, and highlights how such emotional attachment influences interactions with the object (Yip et al., 2018; Li et al., 2020). In the context of tourism, destination attachment refers to the emotional bond with an environment that provides comfort and security, shaping intrinsic personal emotions and behaviours (Kyle et al., 2004). It represents the emotional connection between a tourist and a destination (Krolikowska et al., 2019; Zhou et al., 2023) and is associated with positive emotions and behavioural intentions resulting from interactions with the environment (Hosany et al., 2019; Abbasi et al., 2022).

Attachment theory has been applied in tourism to explore the emotional bonds between tourists and destinations (Krolikowska et al., 2020). However, tourists' emotions are not uniform, especially within the context of film tourism (Yao & Yang, 2024). In film tourism, tourists may have varying degrees of emotional connection and attachment to celebrities before visiting the destinations (Yen & Croy, 2016; Teng & Chen, 2020). Research in the field of film tourism consistently highlights the significant impact of perceived value and destination attachment on tourists' loyalty towards cinematic destinations (Wong & Lai, 2015; Yen & Croy, 2016; Kim et al., 2019).

Research in the field of film tourism consistently highlights the significant impact of perceived value and destination attachment on tourists' loyalty towards cinematic destinations (Wong & Lai, 2015; Yen & Croy, 2016; Kim et al., 2019). Nasir et al. (2022) explore a model involving perceived value, quality of life, place attachment, and destination loyalty. They highlighted the mediating role of place attachment in influencing loyalty behaviours within tourism contexts. Qian and Li (2024) examined the mediating role of place identity between perceived value and behavioural intentions in rural tourism. They emphasised how place identity (part of place attachment) mediates the effect of perceived value on behaviour. Dang and Weiss (2021) conducted a systematic literature review on place attachment and behavioural intentions, consistently finding that place attachment positively affects loyalty and intentions to revisit. However, they do not establish a comprehensive mediating model.

These studies highlight partial mediating effects of place attachment between PV and behavioural intentions, including loyalty, but they do not fully integrate attitudes into the framework. In light of these findings, we propose the following research hypothesis: The relationship between perceived value and loyalty to a film tourism destination is mediated by attachment to the destination and the attitudes of film tourists (**H2**).

2.4 Attitudes

Attitude is defined as a learned predisposition to respond positively or negatively to an object (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). In this context, values and beliefs are key elements in gaining relevant insights to understand tourists' inclinations and preferences (Tyrväinen et al., 2014). It is important to note that attitudes can be positively and negatively influenced by the degree and intensity of importance attributed to certain assumptions, situations, and objects (Rokeach, 1968). Despite this, attitude can be approached from multiple perspectives.

Hernández-Maestro et al. (2006) even suggest a link between attitude and customer satisfaction, where the attitude towards a particular object is reflected in the expectations set at the beginning of the exchange or transaction process, with empirical support for the influence of these expectations. Cinematic content has the power to influence tourist behaviours, prompting both destination hosts and tourists to favour a model that combines cinema with cultural tourism (Lao et al., 2023). This phenomenon is observed in both Eastern and Western contexts, as countries like Japan, Thailand, and the United States have seen a rise in popularity as tourist destinations thanks to the influence of cinema (Wen et al., 2018; Du et al., 2020).

Furthermore, numerous studies have acknowledged the significance of tourist engagement in shaping tourists' experience and behavior or attitude (Kim et al., 2017; Chen & Rahman, 2018; Chen, 2021). Most research on film-related cultural tourism explores tourists' perceptions and attitudes towards film tourism through their active participation (Kim et al., 2019).

2.5 Loyalty towards a film destination

Destination loyalty refers to the intention to revisit and/or recommend a particular location (Oppermann, 2000). This loyalty, experienced by tourists, is inherently tied to the experiences they have at the destination, influencing both current and future decisions specifically related to that place (Oppermann, 2000). It is an essential aspect of tourist behaviour and a critical indicator of success in the tourism industry (Sun et al., 2013; Almeida-Santana & Moreno-Gil, 2018).

According to Stumpf et al. (2020), tourist loyalty stems from customer loyalty and is closely linked to emotions and thoughts. Many researchers have recognised and discussed the importance of tourist loyalty for destinations' growth, success, and sustainability (Stylidis et al., 2020; Dalir, 2023). The concept of loyalty is connected to the destination's potential and is further influenced by a positive evaluation and image, which can boost marketing efforts and financial performance (Zhou et al., 2023).

Understanding the drivers of destination loyalty provides valuable insights and lays the foundation for developing film tourism, influencing those who engage in it (Teng & Chen, 2020). Notably, the study of loyalty in the context of film tourism is nearly nonexistent, with only a few specific studies available on the topic (Lee & Yoon, 2015; Báez-Montenegro & Devesa-Fernández, 2017; Teng & Chen, 2020; Li et al., 2021; Bachman et al., 2022; Wu & Lai, 2022; Zhou et al., 2023).

Loyalty reflects tourists' preferences for tourism products or services and their willingness to engage in repeat consumption (Oppermann, 2000). It is typically assessed using three key indicators: the intention to revisit, positive evaluations, and recommendations of the experience to family and/or friends (Izogo, 2015). Each of these indicators represents a mental state tied to observed behaviours. Therefore, while loyalty may not predict future tourist behaviour with certainty, it serves as a valuable indicator for inferring intentions and can be measured to quantify loyalty, assess its strength, and explore its relationships with other variables (Suhartanto et al., 2020). Scholars have identified factors such as tour quality, experience, satisfaction, image, and trust (Loureiro & González, 2008) as key antecedents of loyalty. Additionally, some studies merge these concepts, addressing the notion of loyalty as an attitudinal construct (Zhou et al., 2023).

2.6 Satisfaction

Tourist satisfaction can be defined as the decision or reaction that follows an emotional experience (Bigne et al., 2001). It is the response elicited by a specific experience (Bayih & Singh, 2020). Generally, satisfaction encompasses the thoughts and emotional state arising after an opportunity (Ranjanthran & Mohammed, 2010; Bayih & Singh, 2020).

The satisfaction derived from the attributes of a product or service is particularly significant in leisure, culture, events, and festivals. The dimensions of satisfaction (Devesa-Fernández et al., 2010) are crucial, as these services often involve multiple elements with a strong experiential nature, which in turn involve a significant emotional component (Çevrimkaya & Zengin, 2023; Hoang, 2023; Hume & Mort, 2010). This is directly connected to film tourism, a concept that highlights the importance of emotions, such as nostalgia (Báez-Montenegro & Devesa-Fernández, 2017; Kim et al., 2019; Jian et al., 2021; Wang, 2023).

Sun et al. (2024) recommend various tourism products or services to enhance the travel experience, thereby increasing satisfaction. Experiences that integrate physical and mental relaxation entertain and foster a deeper connection with the destination. It is also

emphasised that the key to creating a favourable impression of a destination lies in combining these essential factors (Bayih & Singh, 2020), as the previous mentioned.

In this context, Lee and Phau (2018) explored the relationships between perceived value and satisfaction within the context of heritage tourism. Satisfaction in the context of events and festivals has been extensively examined, particularly concerning its influence on loyalty to both the destination and the event itself (Kim et al., 2010b; Yoon et al., 2010). The success of cultural and film events is closely tied to attendee satisfaction, as satisfied participants are more likely to revisit (Báez-Montenegro & Devesa-Fernández, 2017).

Although the complete relationship, wherein satisfaction acts as a mediator between the constructs of perceived value and satisfaction, has not been fully established, we theorize and propose the following hypothesis based on the relationships identified in this review: the relationship between the perceived value of a film destination and loyalty to that destination is mediated by satisfaction with the film destination (**H3**). The proposed structural model is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Proposed structural model

Source: Authors.

3. Methodology

3.1 Questionnaire design and sample

In order to achieve the proposed objectives, a quantitative methodology based on a structured questionnaire was employed, comprising two clearly differentiated sections and informed by prior studies (Baez-Montenegro & Devesa-Fernández, 2017; Chen, 2018; Han et al., 2019; Li et al., 2020; Teng & Chen, 2020). The initial section addressed the model's constructs, including perceived value, satisfaction, destination attachment, attitudes, and destination cinematic loyalty. The indicators were formulated in a seven-point Likert scale, where 1 indicated "Strongly disagree" and 7 indicated "Strongly agree". The second section of the questionnaire was designed to elicit demographic information, including age, gender, educational level and income.

The fieldwork was conducted between June 2020 and December 2022. Initially, it was carried out via an online platform due to the global health crisis. Following lifting COVID-19 restrictions, it was conducted using a paper questionnaire at film festivals and film libraries. The questionnaire was available in Spanish and English to obtain the greatest possible number of valid responses. Ultimately, 768 valid questionnaires were received, but 23% of the questionnaires were excluded due to a high percentage of missing data (Hair et al., 2022).

The sample size was finally set at 590 questionnaires, which is sufficient based on the results of the relevance sampling analysis conducted using the G*Power (1991) software, as presented in Figure 2. Although the figure 2 results indicate a sample size of 205 questionnaires, authors such as Reinartz et al. (2009) recommend an additional 100 cases, resulting in a reference sample size of 305 questionnaires. This is below the final sample size obtained, demonstrating the sampling approach's relevance.

Figure 2 – Sampling relevance

F tests – Linear multiple regression: Fixed model, R ² deviation from zero		
Analysis:	A priori: Compute required sample size	
Input:	Effect size f ²	= 0.15
	α err prob	= 0.01
	Power (1–β err prob)	= 0.99
	Number of predictors	= 3
Output:	Noncentrality parameter λ	= 30.7500000
	Critical F	= 3.8805192
	Numerator df	= 3
	Denominator df	= 201
	Total sample size	= 205
	Actual power	= 0.9901490

Source: Authors.

3.2 Bias

In order to examine the potential for bias, a dual procedure was employed (Podsakoff et al., 2012). Initially, the anonymity of the respondents was ensured, and the questions were formulated in a clear manner, avoiding double entendre and explicitly stating that there were no correct or incorrect responses. Secondly, the Harman test was employed to assess for any potential bias. This statistical test is designed to determine whether a single dominant factor is underlying the observed data, with values exceeding 50% of the total variance indicating potential bias (Fuller et al., 2016). The results of the test are presented in Figure 3, which shows that the percentage of variance explained by the single factor is 41.155%. This evidence indicates that there are no associated issues of bias.

Figure 3 – Sample bias. Harman test

Component	Total	Initial eigenvalues		Extraction sums of squared loadings		
		% of variance	% cumulative	Total	% of variance	% cumulative
1	16,050	41,155	41,155	16,050	41,155	41,155
2	5,169	13,253	54,408			

Source: Authors.

3.3 Preliminary data analysis and sociodemographic profile

Table 1 presents the preliminary data analysis results. The data distribution is not normal, as evidenced by the normality test. Consequently, the data must be treated as non-parametric and the appropriate non-parametric tests must be applied.

Table 1 - Demographics of the participants

	Mean	D.T.	K-S
Attitudes			
<i>Att01</i> – I believe that travelling to a film-related destination is a positive activity	5,677	1,506	0,000c
<i>Att02</i> – I believe that travelling to a film-related destination is a valuable activity	5,408	1,571	0,000c
<i>Att03</i> – I believe that travelling to a film-related destination is an enjoyable activity	5,458	1,576	0,000c
Attachment to the cinematic destination			
<i>PA01</i> – This destination means a lot to me	4,543	1,808	0,000c
<i>PA02</i> – I feel a strong attachment to this destination	4,288	1,852	0,000c
<i>PA03</i> – I strongly identify with this destination	4,215	1,848	0,000c
<i>PA04</i> – This destination is a very special place to me	4,427	1,887	0,000c
<i>PA05</i> – I enjoy visiting this destination more than any other place	4,240	1,813	0,000c
<i>PA06</i> – I derive greater satisfaction from visiting this destination than from any other place or destination	4,083	1,866	0,000c
<i>PA07</i> – Visiting this destination is more important to me than visiting any other place or destination	3,656	1,932	0,000c
<i>PA08</i> – I would not trade the experience I had at this destination for any other place	3,657	1,879	0,000c
Loyalty to the cinematic destination			
<i>LY01</i> – I would like to visit the film-related destination again	4,644	1,953	0,000c
<i>LY02</i> – I would recommend the film-related destination to my family and/or friends	5,192	1,750	0,000c
<i>LY03</i> – I would like to visit other film-related destinations in the future	5,490	1,717	0,000c
<i>LY04</i> – I would recommend other film-related destinations to my family and/or friends	5,231	1,737	0,000c

<i>LY05</i> – I will rewatch certain movies and series to focus on the film-related destinations featured	5,190	1,863	0,000c
Satisfaction with the cinematic destination			
<i>Sat01</i> – One of vacations next year will be dedicated to cinematic tourism	3,808	2,075	0,000c
<i>Sat02</i> – On my next trip, I will engage in cinematic tourism	3,649	1,987	0,000c
<i>Sat03</i> – I am satisfied with my visit to the cinematic destination	5,005	1,769	0,000c
<i>Sat04</i> – I am pleased with my visit to the cinematic destination	5,069	1,797	0,000c
Perceived value of the cinematic destination			
<i>PV01</i> – Identifiable and accessible locations	5,246	1,611	0,000c
<i>PV02</i> – The relevance of the location in the development of the film or series	5,243	1,639	0,000c
<i>PV03</i> – Scenery	5,942	1,401	0,000c
<i>PV04</i> – Variety of flora and fauna	5,192	1,694	0,000c
<i>PV05</i> – Appeal of the cities and towns in the area	5,923	1,334	0,000c
<i>PV06</i> – Hygiene and cleanliness	5,353	1,614	0,000c
<i>PV07</i> – Quality of the infrastructure	5,274	1,580	0,000c
<i>PV08</i> – Personal safety	5,389	1,663	0,000c
<i>PV09</i> – Good nightlife and entertainment	4,858	1,825	0,000c
<i>PV010</i> – Adequate accommodations	5,494	1,516	0,000c
<i>PV011</i> – Attractive local food	5,738	1,452	0,000c
<i>PV012</i> – Good beaches/water sports	5,788	1,897	0,000c
<i>PV013</i> – Friendly and interesting people	5,499	1,628	0,000c
<i>PV014</i> – Interesting cultural attractions	5,807	1,376	0,000c
<i>PV015</i> – Interesting historical attractions	6,771	1,450	0,000c
<i>PV016</i> – Beautiful landscapes and natural attractions	6,005	1,371	0,000c
<i>PV017</i> – Good value for money	5,991	1,344	0,000c
<i>PV018</i> – Unspoiled environment	5,805	1,511	0,000c
<i>PV019</i> – Good climate	5,543	1,520	0,000c

Source: Authors.

Notes: D.T.: Typical deviation; K-S: Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test; c: Lilliefors significance correction

With regard to the demographic profile of the sample, it can be described as a woman with a university degree, either studying or employed in the private sector, with an income of between €1,501 and €2,500 per month. Further details on this profile can be found in Table 2.

Table 2 – Demographic profile of the sample

Variable	N	%	Variable	N	%
Gender			Education level		
Male	249	47,79	Primary education	6	1,15
Female	261	50,10	Secondary education	98	18,85
Non-binary	11	2,11	University degree	220	42,31
			Degree/Master`s degree/PhD	196	37,69
Professional category			Monthly household income (€/month)		
Self-employed	44	8,48	Less than 700€	34	7,0
Public employee	107	20,62	From 700€ to 1000€	78	16,05
Private sector employee	113	21,77	From 1001€ to 1500€	111	22,84
Freelancer	31	5,97	From 1501€ to 2500€	134	27,57
Student	163	31,41	From 2501€ to 3500€	75	15,43
Unemployed	33	6,36	More than 3500€	54	11,11
Retired	18	3,47			
Housework	10	1,93			

Source: Authors.

3.4 Statistical Analysis

A variety of statistical software was employed for different purposes during the study. Initially, G*Power was employed to determine the minimum relevant sample size. Subsequently, SPSS v.24 was used for data tabulation, preliminary analysis, and the Harman test. Finally, SmartPLS 4.1, a partial least squares program, was utilised for structural modelling, as it is a leading software for structural modelling.

Given the explanatory nature of this research (Henseler, 2021), the focus will be on the explanatory power of endogenous variables, the size of the effect, and the testing of structural relationships.

4. Analysis of Results and Discussion

4.1 Measurement model analysis

At the individual level, particularly in Mode A compounds, evaluation is conducted using factor loads, which must be equal to or greater than 0.707 (Carmines and Zeller, 1979; Ali et al., 2018). In order to conduct the study, the indicators pertaining to the construct "Value Perceived" (PV01, PV08, PV11 and PV18) were excluded on the grounds that their factor loadings were below the threshold of 0.707. This resulted in an improvement in the internal consistency of the model. The indicators of Compounds Mode B are tested through the weights, which all prove to be significant. Furthermore, the inflation factor test (VIF) is employed to ascertain the potential for multicollinearity between the indicators. Values of VIF in excess of 3 would indicate the presence of multicollinearity (Hair, Risher, Sarstedt and Ringle, 2019).

The internal consistency was evaluated using the Dijkstra-Henseler reliability composite (Rho_A), which is considered the most reliable measure of internal consistency (Dijkstra & Henseler, 2015). Conversely, the convergent validity, measured by the Average Variance Extracted (AVE), provides the aggregated variance each construct derives from its indicators. As Henseler, Hubona and Ray (2016) proposed, the minimum acceptable values for Rho_A and AVE are 0.70 and 0.50, respectively. The results of the reliability and validity analysis of the measurement model at the individual level and at the level of internal consistency are presented in Table 3.

The results of Table 3 demonstrate, on the one hand, the excellent reliability of Mode A indicators, as evidenced by the fact that the majority of the factor loads are equal to or greater than 0.707. In contrast, the Mode B indicators are significant and free from issues of multicollinearity. On the other hand, at the level of internal consistency, the reliability of the construct is confirmed by the values obtained for Rho_A, all of which are above 0.80, indicating that each group of indicators is measuring its respective construct with precision.

Table 3 – Reliability and validity analysis at the individual level

	Loads (Sig.)	Weights (Sig.)	VIF	Rho_A	AVE
Attitudes				1,000	n/a
Att01	0,921 (0,000)	0,437 (0,000)	2,857		
Att02	0,895 (0,000)	0,380 (0,000)	2,761		
Att03	0,707 (0,000)	0,355 (0,000)	1,350		
Loyalty to the cinematic destination				0,930	0,774
LY01	0,905 (0,000)				
LY02	0,915 (0,000)				
LY03	0,919 (0,000)				
LY04	0,821 (0,000)				
LY05	0,831 (0,000)				
Perceived value on the cinematic destination				0,940	0,529
PV02	0,714 (0,000)				
PV03	0,625 (0,000)				
PV04	0,750 (0,000)				
PV05	0,754 (0,000)				
PV06	0,761 (0,000)				
PV07	0,717 (0,000)				
PV09	0,744 (0,000)				
PV010	0,737 (0,000)				
PV012	0,719 (0,000)				
PV013	0,786 (0,000)				
PV014	0,728 (0,000)				
PV015	0,775 (0,000)				
PV016	0,738 (0,000)				
PV017	0,722 (0,000)				
PV018	0,721 (0,000)				
Attachment to the cinematic destination				0,942	0,701
PA01	0,765 (0,000)				
PA02	0,808 (0,000)				
PA03	0,786 (0,000)				
PA04	0,900 (0,000)				
PA05	0,880 (0,000)				
PA06	0,873 (0,000)				
PA07	0,874 (0,000)				
PA08	0,802 (0,000)				
Satisfaction with the cinematic destination				0,875	0,704
Sat01	0,749 (0,000)				
Sat02	0,888 (0,000)				
Sat03	0,894 (0,000)				
Sat04	0,816 (0,000)				

Source: Authors.

Notes: VIF: Variance Inflation Factor; Rho_A: Composite Reliability of the Dijkstra-Henseler Scale; AVE: Average Variance Extracted; n/a: Not Applicable

Discriminant validity refers to the extent to which a given compound differs from the remainder of the structural model compounds. In order to demonstrate the existence of discriminant validity, the value of the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio must be less than 0.85 (Kline, 2011). Table 4 presents the results of the discriminant analysis, which demonstrate the aforementioned validity, indicating that each compound is empirically distinct from the remainder of the structural model.

Table 4 – Discriminant Validity. Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio

	Loyalty	Perceived value	Place Attachment	Satisfaction
Loyalty				
Perceived value	0,451			
Place attachment	0,734	0,480		
Satisfaction	0,806	0,431	0,767	

Source: Authors.

4.2 Structural Model Analysis

Given the explanatory nature of the research (Henseler, 2021), the explanatory power of the endogenous variables will be tested using the coefficient of determination (R²). Secondly, the effect size will determine the impact of exogenous variables on endogenous variables. Finally, hypothesis testing will be conducted to assess the structural relationships that constitute the model structure.

In terms of explanatory power, the coefficient of determination measures the variance that a set of exogenous variables can explain with respect to their endogenous variable. Hair et al. (2014) established weak, moderate, and substantial levels of explanatory power for values of R² greater than 0.25, 0.50, and 0.75, respectively. Concerning the effect size (f²), the authors of reference, such as Cohen (1988, 2013), indicate three categories of effect size: small, moderate and large. The corresponding values of f² for these categories are 0.02, 0.15 and 0.35, respectively. Hair, Hult, Ringle and Sarstedt (2019) recommend the use of confidence intervals to confirm the statistical relevance of the associated effect size values.

Table 5 presents the results of the explanatory power and effect size. It is noteworthy that the moderate explanatory power of attitudes and destination cinematic loyalty is evident from the table. Notably, place attachment accounts for 69.38% of the variance in attitude and 55.86% of the variance in destination cinematic loyalty.

With regard to the effect size, the results are in alignment with the preceding power of explanation. The Place Attachment and satisfaction were found to exert considerable and meaningful effects on attitude and loyalty towards a cinematic destination. Conversely, no evidence was found to support the hypothesis that attitude and perceived value exert any influence on cinematic destination loyalty (Table 5).

Table 5 – Explanatory power and explained variance

	R ²	f ²	Corr.	E.V.	f ² (Sig.) - Interpretation
Place Attachment Perceived Value	0,208	0,456	0,456	18,87%	0,206(0,002) – Moderate and significant
Attitude Place Attachment	0,694	0,842	0,842	69,38%	2,427(0,000) – Big and significant
Satisfaction Perceived Value	0,159	0,398	0,398	11,28%	0,189(0,000) – Moderate and significant
Loyalty Attitude	0,686	0,120	0,612	7,34%	0,015(0,187) – No effect
Perceived Value		0,099	0,556	5,40%	0,024(0,204) – No effect
Satisfaction		0,715	0,817	55,86%	0,918(0,000) – Big and significant

Source: Authors.

Using the bootstrapping technique, a hypothesis contrast was finally carried out, with 10,000 samples (Streukens & Leroi-Werelds, 2016). The corrected confidence intervals were obtained, as the non-parametric nature of the data was also confirmed through the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (see Table 1). The results of the hypothesis contrast are presented in Table 6.

Table 6 – Hypothesis Testing and Mediation Analysis

Direct effects	f ²	BC CI (95%)	
		2,5%	97,5%
H1(C): Perceived Value → Loyalty	0,099 ^{NSIG}	-0,020	0,158

a1: Perceived Value → Place Attachment	0,456 ^{SIG}	0,316	0,519	
b1: Place Attachment → Attitude	0,842 ^{SIG}	0,797	0,868	
c1: Attitude → Loyalty	0,120 ^{SIG}	0,027	0,217	
a2: Perceived Value → Satisfaction	0,398 ^{SIG}	0,217	0,456	
b2: Satisfaction → Loyalty	0,715 ^{SIG}	0,616	0,779	
Indirect effects				VAF
H2: a1xb1xc1	0,046 ^{SIG}	0,009	0,080	31,75% - FM
H3: a2xb2	0,285 ^{SIG}	0,153	0,325	74,18% - FM

Source: Authors.

Notes: Path coefficient; BC CI: Bias Corrected Confidence Interval; VAF: Variance Accounted For; FM: Full Mediation; sig: Significant; NSIG: Not significant

The results of Table 6 demonstrate the existence of several mediating variables (Nitzl et al., 2016). It is noteworthy that place attachment and attitudes mediate the perceived value and loyalty to cinematic destinations. Similarly, satisfaction also has a mediating effect on the perceived value and cinematic destination loyalty. Both of these effects are considered to be total. Figure 3 illustrates the final structural model results.

Figure 3 – Final structural model

Source: Authors.

The results of the study corroborate the growing influence of film tourism on tourist behaviour, in alignment with prior research that underscores the pivotal role of media in shaping destination perceptions (Kim & Kim, 2017; Wray & Croy, 2015). The growth in tourist numbers, from 40 million to 80 million between 2012 and 2018, correlates with the increase in media consumption (TCI Research, 2018; Ericsson ConsumerLab, 2017), thereby reinforcing the assertion that film plays a pivotal role in the promotion of tourism (Hudson & Ritchie, 2006).

The strong emotional ties that tourists form with film locations are in alignment with the findings of previous studies on the influence of cinematic nostalgia (Croy & Heitmann, 2011; Roesch, 2009). The high scores for destination attachment indicate that film-related travel has the potential to transform these locations into places of personal significance, extending their significance beyond that of mere tourist attractions (Cardoso et al., 2017).

Furthermore, the year-round appeal of film tourism is in stark contrast to the seasonal nature of traditional coastal tourism, thereby supporting the conclusions of Zielinski and Botero (2019). The study corroborates the assertion that film-related tourism provides destinations with the potential to attract visitors throughout the year (Domínguez-Azcue et al., 2021). Furthermore, the findings lend support to the proposition that tourist loyalty fostered by film experiences is consistent with the conclusions of earlier research by Hudson and Ritchie (2006). This suggests that the immersive quality of film tourism is conducive to repeat visits and recommendations, which ultimately contribute to the sustainability of destinations.

The hypothesis testing and mediation analysis revealed that place attachment and satisfaction fully mediate the relationship between perceived value and loyalty. This finding highlights the crucial role of these mediators in the path from perceived value to loyalty, indicating that perceived value influences loyalty indirectly through place attachment and satisfaction.

Overall, this study enhances the understanding of how place attachment and satisfaction mediate the relationship between perceived value and loyalty in the context of a cinematic destination. The results emphasise the importance of these mediators and offer insights into the underlying mechanisms of consumer loyalty in this setting. Future research could explore additional variables or contexts to further validate and expand these findings.

5. Conclusions, limitations, implications and future research

The findings of the study indicate that attachment to place and satisfaction act as key mediators in the relationship between perceived value and tourist loyalty towards cinematic tourist destinations. The data suggest that tourists value cinematic tourist destinations for their visible characteristics and the emotional connections they establish with these places. Satisfaction with the experience and emotional attachment play an important role in the retention of tourists, suggesting that offering memorable experiences may strengthen such loyalty.

The research is limited in that the results may not be applicable to other geographical contexts or types of film locations, given that the research focused on a specific sample. Furthermore, additional variables were not considered, such as cultural differences and the availability of cinematic-related services. Nevertheless, the results have significant implications for destination managers, who can leverage these insights to develop strategies that foster place attachment and visitor satisfaction, thereby enhancing loyalty and promoting sustainable tourism.

It would be beneficial for future studies to examine how cultural and regional characteristics influence the relationship between perceived value, place attachment, and brand loyalty among different types of cinematic destinations. It would also be beneficial to investigate the impact of new technologies and digital platforms on the perception of value of these destinations. Furthermore, future studies could examine how different cinematic genres and types of productions affect attitudes and place attachment, providing a more comprehensive understanding of how these factors influence tourist experiences and visitor loyalty.

The results obtained reinforce the theory that the image of destinations is not solely based on their visual appeal but also on the symbolism they acquire through cinema. Additionally, this study highlights the contribution of sustainability to destinations by reducing seasonality and diversifying the tourism offering beyond mass tourism.

Regarding managerial implications, the findings suggest that stakeholders, such as destination managers, should promote immersive experiences that strengthen visitors' attachment to the destination and events related to films and television series shot in the location. These initiatives aim to enhance the destination's added value, ultimately fostering greater loyalty among tourists. In line with this approach, it is also recommended that marketing campaigns focus on the emotional connection that tourists develop with cinematic settings, fostering a deeper emotional bond between the destination and its visitors.

Credit author statement

All authors have contributed equally. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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